

Trophic interactions shape ciguatera risk in a warming ocean

Ciguatera is one of the most widespread marine poisonings worldwide, caused by the consumption of fish that bioaccumulate ciguatoxins (CTXs) produced by dinoflagellate species belonging to the genus *Gambierdiscus*. Its expansion into non-endemic regions reflects the combined influence of climate change and the globalization of seafood trade [1]. Sea surface temperature acts as a primary large-scale constraint regulating *Gambierdiscus* growth (optimum $\geq 29^\circ\text{C}$), while species composition ultimately modulates toxicity and outbreak intensity. However, this relationship is nonlinear, with thermal thresholds and climatic variability (e.g. ENSO) limiting straightforward predictions [2].

Beyond environmental drivers, mounting evidence indicates that ciguatera occurrence is strongly shaped by the taxonomic composition of *Gambierdiscus*, given the pronounced interspecific variability in toxicity [3]. Within marine food webs, CTXs are progressively amplified, concentrating risk at higher trophic levels [4]. At the physiological level, these toxins disrupt ion channel function, increasing neuronal excitability and underpinning the predominance and persistence of neurological symptoms [5]. Together, these processes connect organismal toxicity mechanisms with ecosystem-level transfer dynamics. Ciguatera thus emerges as a multiscale phenomenon driven by the interaction between climate forcing, microalgal diversity, and trophic structure.

Addressing this complexity requires conceptual and quantitative frameworks capable of isolating key mechanisms. In this context, a mathematical model of ciguatoxin transfer was developed as part of a master's thesis at the Universidad Nacional de Colombia. To isolate the trophic dimension, the model adopts a predator-prey framework with a Holling type I functional response, coupling population dynamics and toxin fluxes through a system of ordinary differential equations. Rather than explicitly incorporating climate variability, the model focuses on the trophic processes that regulate toxin amplification under given environmen-

tal conditions [6]. Both analytical and numerical results demonstrate that toxin accumulation is not solely driven by the presence of toxic microalgae. Instead, it emerges from the interaction between trophic structure and population dynamics. System stability, by controlling population persistence and interaction strength, plays a central role in regulating toxin retention and amplification across trophic levels. The model exhibits multiple equilibrium states, although only a subset is ecologically meaningful. Simulations further show that relatively small shifts in population structure can trigger contrasting toxin accumulation regimes, providing a mechanistic basis for the emergence of ciguatera outbreaks.

Beyond its theoretical contribution, this framework reframes ciguatera as an emergent property of trophic systems. By explicitly linking toxin trans-

fer to ecological interactions, it offers a pathway from reactive monitoring toward predictive understanding. In this sense, the model can be viewed as a conceptual prototype of a risk simulator grounded in trophic ecology, capable of identifying conditions under which ciguatoxins are likely to amplify through food webs (Fig. 1).

This perspective opens new avenues for management. By identifying key trophic pathways and species that disproportionately contribute to toxin magnification, the model can inform targeted consumption advisories and risk-based fisheries management. When coupled with environmental data, it also provides a foundation for spatial risk mapping and early warning systems, particularly in reef ecosystems subject to disturbance.

A key next step is to move from this simplified framework toward a data-informed, operational tool. This will require incorporating nonlinear trophic interactions, expanding food web complexity, and integrating environmental

Fig. 1. Conceptual model: Ciguatoxin transfer in marine food webs.

drivers such as temperature variability and habitat disturbance. Calibration and validation with empirical data on cell densities, toxin concentrations, and ecosystem dynamics will be essential to generate robust predictions. The inclusion of spatial structure and coupling with human health risk modules would further enhance its applicability.

Although deliberately simplified, this approach underscores a central point: ciguatera risk cannot be understood without explicitly accounting for ecological interactions. By linking energy flow with toxin transfer, this framework provides a tractable, mechanistic bridge between ecosystem dynamics and toxin exposure, ultimately improving our ability to anticipate risk in a changing ocean.

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A new global reference for HAB and toxin monitoring has just been released

The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO, and the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) have jointly published comprehensive guidance on the monitoring of algal toxins in bivalve molluscs, filling a long-standing gap identified by the international HAB community. The document (FAO Food Safety and Quality Series No. 34, 2026) provides, for the first time, an integrated and globally applicable framework linking harmful algal bloom (HAB) monitoring, toxin analysis, and the management of shellfish harvesting areas.

The guidance is designed as a practical tool for national authorities, monitoring programmes, and laboratories. It brings together approaches for phytoplankton monitoring, toxin detection, and risk-based management, covering both pre-harvest and post-harvest stages. Particular attention is given to adapting monitoring strategies to local conditions, including the use of early warning systems, sentinel species, and flexible sampling schemes that reflect regional HAB dynamics. In this way, the document supports both public health protection and compliance with international trade requirements.

Developed following an expert meeting held in Rome in October 2025, the guidance reflects input from an international group of specialists across disciplines. It aligns with existing Codex Alimentarius texts and complements earlier guidance documents, while specifically addressing the role of toxic microalgae and marine biotoxins in shell-

fish safety. As HAB events continue to expand and intensify in many regions, this publication provides timely and much-needed support for harmonized monitoring and management practices worldwide.

The document is freely available at: DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4060/cd8990en>

